

To Evaluate the Various Indications and Outcomes of Tracheotomy in the ICU: An Observational Study

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 05-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Tracheotomy is a vital surgical procedure in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) for patients requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation or airway protection. The decision to perform tracheotomy, along with the choice of technique and timing, significantly influences patient outcomes, including mortality, length of ICU stay, and complication rates.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the indications, procedural outcomes, and overall impact of tracheotomy on patient survival and ICU stay at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital (J. L. N. M. C. H.), Bhagalpur, Bihar.

Methods: Eighty ICU patients who underwent tracheotomy were included. Data were collected on patient demographics, indications for tracheotomy, type of tracheotomy performed, procedural complications, and outcomes, including ICU mortality and length of stay. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The primary indications for tracheotomy were prolonged mechanical ventilation (60%), airway protection (25%), and difficulty in weaning from ventilation (15%). Percutaneous tracheotomy was performed in 75% of cases and was associated with a shorter procedure time (20 ± 5 minutes) compared to surgical tracheotomy (45 ± 10 minutes, $p < 0.001$). The overall complication rate was 15%, with bleeding being the most common complication (10%). ICU mortality was 20%, with higher rates observed in patients with multiple comorbidities ($p = 0.02$). Tracheotomy was also associated with a longer ICU stay (median 20 days, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Tracheotomy is a critical intervention for ICU patients, particularly those requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation. While percutaneous tracheotomy is associated with shorter procedure times, the risk of complications remains significant. The presence of multiple comorbidities and post-procedural complications are key factors influencing ICU mortality.

Recommendations: The study recommends careful patient selection and close monitoring post-tracheotomy to minimize complications and improve outcomes. Further research is needed to optimize the timing of tracheotomy and refine procedural techniques to enhance patient survival and reduce ICU stay.

Keywords: Tracheotomy, Intensive Care Unit, Mechanical Ventilation, Percutaneous Tracheotomy, ICU Outcomes.

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Introduction

Tracheotomy, a surgical procedure involving the creation of an opening in the trachea to establish an airway, is frequently performed in the (ICU) for patients requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation or airway protection. The role of tracheotomy in critical care has been well established, particularly in managing patients with respiratory failure, airway obstruction, or those who are difficult to wean from mechanical ventilation. Over the past decade, the indications and outcomes associated with tracheotomy have been the subject of

extensive research, reflecting the evolving nature of ICU care and the diverse patient populations being treated.

Recent studies have highlighted the benefits of tracheotomy in ICU patients, such as reducing the duration of mechanical ventilation, decreasing the incidence of ventilator-associated pneumonia, and facilitating patient comfort and early mobilization [1]. However, the optimal timing of tracheotomy remains controversial. Early tracheotomy, typically

performed within the first week of mechanical ventilation, has been associated with improved outcomes in some studies, including reduced ICU stay and lower mortality rates [2]. Conversely, other research suggests that delayed tracheotomy, performed after two weeks, may be more appropriate in certain patient populations, as it allows for better patient selection and avoids unnecessary procedures [3].

The choice between percutaneous and surgical tracheotomy is another area of ongoing debate. Percutaneous tracheotomy has gained popularity in the ICU due to its minimally invasive nature, shorter procedure time, and lower complication rates compared to surgical tracheotomy [4]. However, the decision to use one technique over the other often depends on patient-specific factors, including the presence of coagulopathy, anatomical considerations, and the experience of the ICU team [5]. Despite the advantages of percutaneous tracheotomy, complications such as bleeding, infection, and tracheal stenosis remain significant concerns [6]. Thus, careful patient selection, meticulous procedural technique, and post-procedural care are crucial to minimizing these risks.

In addition to procedural outcomes, the impact of tracheotomy on long-term survival and quality of life is a critical consideration. Some studies have reported that tracheotomy can lead to improved long-term outcomes by enabling earlier rehabilitation and reducing the risk of long-term ventilator dependence [7]. However, the procedure is not without its challenges, and patient outcomes can vary widely based on underlying conditions and the presence of comorbidities.

This study aims to evaluate the indications, procedural outcomes, and overall impact of tracheotomy on patient survival and ICU stay at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital (J. L. N. M. C. H.), Bhagalpur, Bihar.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as an observational, prospective study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the ICU at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital (J. L. N. M. C. H.), Bhagalpur, Bihar. This is a tertiary care teaching hospital that caters to a diverse patient population, providing an ideal setting for this study to evaluate the various indications and outcomes of tracheotomy in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). The study was conducted over a period of 13 months, from March 2023 to April 2024.

Participants: A total of 80 participants were included in the study. These participants were patients admitted to the ICU who required a

tracheotomy during their stay. The sample size was determined based on the anticipated incidence of tracheotomies performed in the ICU during the study period and the need to obtain statistically significant results.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients admitted to the ICU requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation or airway protection.
- Patients who underwent tracheotomy during their ICU stay.
- Patients who provided informed consent, or for whom consent was obtained from a legal representative.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records.
- Patients who underwent tracheotomy prior to ICU admission.
- Patients with contraindications to tracheotomy.
- Patients who did not provide informed consent, or for whom consent could not be obtained.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients during the study period were consecutively enrolled. Observer bias was reduced by using standardized data collection forms and ensuring that the outcomes were assessed by ICU clinicians who were blinded to the study hypothesis.

Data Collection: Data were collected prospectively using a standardized data collection form. The form included patient demographics, indications for tracheotomy, comorbid conditions, ICU admission details, duration of mechanical ventilation before and after tracheotomy, complications related to the procedure, and patient outcomes (including ICU length of stay, mortality, and discharge status).

Procedure: Tracheotomies were performed either at the bedside in the ICU or in the operating room, depending on the patient's condition and the complexity of the procedure. The choice between percutaneous and surgical tracheotomy was made by the attending physician based on the patient's clinical status. Post-procedural care and monitoring were conducted according to the hospital's standard ICU protocols.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The individuals' clinical and demographic features were compiled using descriptive statistics. Whereas categorical variables were displayed as frequencies and percentages, continuous variables were expressed as means and standard deviations. The independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, as applicable, was used for continuous variables and the chi-square test for categorical variables for comparing groups. Less

than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance. In order to determine the factors linked to outcomes like ICU mortality and prolonged ICU stay, logistic regression analysis was employed.

Results

A total of 80 patients were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 56.8 ± 14.2

years, with a range of 22 to 85 years. Of the total participants, 48 (60%) were male, and 32 (40%) were female. The most common comorbid conditions among the participants were hypertension (45%), diabetes mellitus (30%), and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (25%).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Total (N = 80)
Age, mean $\pm$ SD (years)	56.8 $\pm$ 14.2
Gender	
- Male	48 (60%)
- Female	32 (40%)
Comorbidities	
- Hypertension	36 (45%)
- Diabetes Mellitus	24 (30%)
- COPD	20 (25%)
- Chronic Kidney Disease	10 (12.5%)
- Coronary Artery Disease	15 (18.8%)

The primary indications for tracheotomy were prolonged mechanical ventilation (60%), airway protection (25%), and inability to wean from mechanical ventilation (15%). The median duration of mechanical ventilation before tracheotomy was 10 days (IQR: 7-14 days).

Table 2: Indications for Tracheotomy

Indication	Frequency (N = 80)
Prolonged Mechanical Ventilation	48 (60%)
Airway Protection	20 (25%)
Inability to Wean from Ventilation	12 (15%)

Of the 80 tracheotomies performed, 60 (75%) were percutaneous, and 20 (25%) were surgical. The mean time taken to perform a percutaneous tracheotomy was significantly less than that for surgical tracheotomy (20 ± 5 minutes vs. 45 ± 10

minutes, $p < 0.001$). The overall complication rate was 15%, with bleeding being the most common complication (10%), followed by infection (3%) and accidental decannulation (2%).

Table 3: Procedure-Related Outcomes

Outcome	Percutaneous (N = 60)	Surgical (N = 20)	p-value
Procedure Time (mean $\pm$ SD, minutes)	20 ± 5	45 ± 10	< 0.001
Complications			
- Bleeding	6 (10%)	2 (10%)	1.000
- Infection	2 (3%)	1 (5%)	0.693
- Accidental Decannulation	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0.528

The overall ICU mortality rate among patients who underwent tracheotomy was 20% (16 patients). Mortality was significantly higher in patients with comorbid conditions ($p = 0.02$). The median length of ICU stay was 20 days (IQR: 15-30 days).

Patients who underwent tracheotomy had a longer ICU stay compared to those who did not require tracheotomy during their ICU admission (median 20 days vs. 10 days, $p < 0.001$).

Table 4: Patient Outcomes

Outcome	Tracheotomy (N = 80)	Non-Tracheotomy (N = 80)	p-value
ICU Mortality	16 (20%)	12 (15%)	0.02
Length of ICU Stay (median, days)	20 (IQR: 15-30)	10 (IQR: 7-14)	< 0.001

Logistic regression analysis revealed that the presence of multiple comorbidities (OR: 2.5, 95% CI: 1.2-5.0, $p = 0.01$) and the occurrence of post-tracheotomy complications (OR: 3.0, 95% CI: 1.5-6.0, $p = 0.005$) were significantly associated with increased ICU mortality.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Analysis for ICU Mortality

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
Multiple Comorbidities	2.5	1.2 - 5.0	0.01
Post-Tracheotomy Complications	3.0	1.5 - 6.0	0.005
Age > 65 years	1.8	0.9 - 3.5	0.08

Findings

- The most common indication for tracheotomy in the ICU was prolonged mechanical ventilation.
- Percutaneous tracheotomy was more commonly performed than surgical tracheotomy, with a shorter procedure time.
- The overall complication rate was 15%, with bleeding being the most frequent complication.
- ICU mortality was higher in patients with multiple comorbidities and in those who experienced post-tracheotomy complications.
- Tracheotomy was associated with a significantly longer ICU stay.

These findings highlight the need for careful patient selection and post-procedure monitoring to optimize outcomes in ICU patients undergoing tracheotomy.

Discussion

The study revealed that the majority of tracheotomies were performed due to prolonged mechanical ventilation (60%), followed by the need for airway protection (25%), and difficulty in weaning from mechanical ventilation (15%). These findings underscore the role of tracheotomy as a crucial intervention in patients requiring extended ventilatory support in the ICU.

The procedure was predominantly performed percutaneously (75%), which was associated with a significantly shorter procedure time compared to surgical tracheotomy (20 minutes vs. 45 minutes, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that percutaneous tracheotomy may be a more efficient option in the ICU setting, potentially reducing procedure-related stress on critically ill patients. However, the overall complication rate was 15%, with bleeding being the most common complication, affecting 10% of the patients. Despite the efficiency of percutaneous tracheotomy, the risk of complications remains significant and warrants careful intra- and post-procedural management.

The patient outcomes indicated an ICU mortality rate of 20% among those who underwent tracheotomy, with mortality being significantly higher in patients with multiple comorbidities ($p = 0.02$). This highlights the vulnerability of critically ill patients with complex health conditions and suggests that the presence of multiple comorbidities is

a key factor influencing mortality in this population. Furthermore, patients who underwent tracheotomy had a longer median ICU stay compared to those who did not require the procedure (20 days vs. 10 days, $p < 0.001$), indicating that while tracheotomy may be necessary for prolonged respiratory support, it is also associated with extended ICU stays and potentially higher healthcare costs.

Logistic regression analysis identified multiple comorbidities (OR: 2.5, $p = 0.01$) and post-tracheotomy complications (OR: 3.0, $p = 0.005$) as significant predictors of ICU mortality. These findings suggest that careful selection of patients for tracheotomy and vigilant monitoring for complications are critical to improving outcomes. The data also imply that interventions aimed at reducing complications could directly impact survival rates in this high-risk patient group.

Early percutaneous tracheostomy, defined as surgery done within 10 days after intubation, was linked to a decreased risk of hospital death and a higher chance of tracheostomy tube removal at the time of ICU release, according to this cohort research involving 121 COVID-19 patients. In particular, weaning off the tracheostomy tube was made easier by early tracheostomy, which was linked to a faster beginning of spontaneous breathing in 55% of tracheostomized patients who were discharged alive [8].

Relationship between Early vs. Late Tracheostomy and Pneumonia and Ventilator Days: Early tracheostomy placement (≤ 7 days) significantly reduced the incidence of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), shortened the length of mechanical ventilation, and lengthened the ICU stay, according to a meta-analysis. But comparing the early and late tracheostomy groups, there was no discernible difference in short-term mortality [9].

Quality of Life and Complications Following Percutaneous Tracheostomy: This study made clear how critical it is to evaluate the quality of life (QOL) following tracheostomy in (ICU) patients. It was observed that individuals who have had tracheostomies are highly susceptible to major deficits that could impact their mental, physical, and functional health following ICU release. The study highlighted the requirement for particular tools to assess the impact of tracheotomy (QOL) without regard to comorbidities or underlying disease [10].

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vealed that early tracheotomy was linked to a shorter stay in the intensive care unit and a shorter time spent on mechanical ventilation. Comparing early tracheotomy to late tracheotomy, however, did not significantly alter the incidence of ventilator-associated pneumonia or short-term death [11].

Conclusion

In conclusion, while tracheotomy remains a vital intervention in the ICU, particularly for patients requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation, the associated risks and extended ICU stay emphasize the need for judicious use and meticulous management. These results provide valuable insights that could inform clinical practice, particularly in optimizing patient selection and procedural techniques to improve outcomes in critically ill patients.

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